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Wearable Textile-based Chemiresistive pH Sensors with MXene-Chitosan Composite

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Abstract:

pH monitoring is very essential for analyzing human health. Any deviations from standard pH range can cause some medical conditions such as metabolic disorders and wound healing complications. Thus its monitoring is very crucial. Recently, some wearable electrochemical and colorimetric sensors utilizing different nanomaterials have been reported for monitoring the pH noninvasively [1-2]. However, they are limited by complex fabrication processes. In this work, we proposed textile-based chemiresistive pH sensors and examined MXene-chitosan (MX-CS) as a sensing material. $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene and chitosan solutions were initially synthesized. Afterward, MXene and MX-CS sensors (Figure 1a) were fabricated by depositing these sensing materials onto interdigitated textile electrodes (IDEs), followed by drying them at 40 °C in open air. Before that, IDE electrodes were prepared by cutting the thin conductive fabric using a cutter plotter machine and transferring them onto the adhesive tape. Morphological study revealed the presence of MXene-chitosan material covering the textile. The average electrical resistance (dry condition) of MXene and MX-CS were measured to be 1.17 M Ω and 0.765 M Ω , respectively. The chemiresistive response of textile sensors with MX-CS was investigated in buffers with a pH range of 4–8 (Figure 1b). The sensor's response was found to be linear with a coefficient of correlation $R^2 \sim 0.934$ whereas, MXene-based sensor showed $R^2 \sim 0.732$. The sensitivity of MXene-chitosan-based sensor was found to be 210.5 Ω /pH, revealing a higher value than that of MXene only (136.8 Ω /pH). Such wearable and biocompatible pH sensors are highly suitable for continuous monitoring of pH variations in the body.

Keywords: pH sensing, MXene, chitosan, wearable, textile sensors, chemiresistive, biosensors, health-care, biomedical applications.

Figure 1: (a) Illustration of components of textile-based pH sensor with MX-CS sensing layer. (b) Sensing response of MX-CS-based pH sensor. The insets show the photograph of the sensing device (left) and the optical microscopic image of MX-CS coated fabric (right).

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